

Pest management and control RODENTS

Squirrels as rodent pests of rice in Bangladesh

Shamsul Alam, M. Aminul Haque, and M. Azizul Haque, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

Rats are important rice pests, especially in deepwater rice areas of Bangladesh, but

there has been no record of squirrels as rice pests. During a tour of southwestern Bangladesh in July 1979, we not only received reports of squirrel damage, but also observed a group of squirrels damaging the dryland aus rice crop in the Ganges-Kobadak project area, Kushtia district. The five-striped Indian squirrel *Funabulus pennati* Wroughton eats grain

the way rats do. It is important in three districts of Bangladesh — Kushtia, Jessore, and Khulna — bordering West Bengal, India. It has not been found in other Bangladesh districts except for one reference from Sylhet.

Other squirrel species, including the five-striped Indian squirrel, are serious pests of vegetables, fruits, and nuts. ■

Irrigation and water management

A simple microlysimeter to measure transpiration and evapotranspiration in wetland rice fields

V. S. Tomar and J. C. O'Toole, Agronomy Department, International Rice Research Institute

The measurement of water loss as transpiration and evapotranspiration (ET) for each hour or each day in the field is difficult because the available methods are either expensive or inaccurate. A simple microlysimeter for use in irrigated wetland rice fields was designed and tested. It consists of a polyvinylchloride (PVC) cylinder, sealed at the lower end and connected to a water reservoir-cum-manometer with flexible tubing (see figure). Water in the microlysimeter was maintained at a constant level equivalent to the height of flooded water in the surrounding field with the Mariotte system. Measurement of the water loss from the reservoir-manometer represents the transpiration or evapotranspiration during a time interval.

The microlysimeters were calibrated in the laboratory, then installed in plots in a puddled field. The soil was excavated and the cylinders were installed 50 cm deep, leaving 10 cm of the cylinder's top portion above the soil surface (see figure). The cylinders were so installed that the rice hill in each lysimeter became an integral part of the 20- x 20-cm field

Cross section of installed microlysimeters for measuring evapotranspiration (A) and transpiration (B) in wetland rice.

planting pattern. Transpiration was measured by carefully covering the PVC cylinders with perspex sheets and checking the evaporation from the water surface in the cylinders. The trial was

replicated four times.

To verify the reliability and accuracy of the microlysimeter results, 40- x 40-cm tanks, each holding 4 hills, were installed along with these units in 1978-79.

Three rice varieties – IR20, IR36, and Dular – were grown in both types of units. ET data were collected from the 2 units from 15 days after planting until flowering. There was good agreement of data obtained from each type of unit. When graphed, the distribution of data points along a 1:1 line indicated that both microlysimeters are reliable and accurate for ET measurement in wetland rice fields.

The table shows an example of ET rates for the 3 cultivars and pan

Evapotranspiration rate at maximum tillering growth stage on 1 clear day for 3 cultivars of rice grown at IRRI in the 1978 dry and wet seasons.

Date	Season	Evapotranspiration (mm/day)			Av pan evaporation (mm/day)	Solar radiation (cal/cm ² per day)
		IR36	IR20	Dular		
13 Apr	Dry	10.0	9.0	8.2	8.8	663
25 Sep	Wet	5.7	4.3	7.8	4.8	571
19 Dec	Wet	4.2	4.3	6.2	4.2	476

evaporation and solar radiation values on 3 clear days at about the maximum tillering stage in the 1978 dry and wet seasons.

Simple to fabricate and maintain the

microlysimeters can be made locally and handled easily. The microlysimeter principle might also be applied to ecological studies of water use by non-crop aquatic and semi-aquatic species. ■

Soil and crop management

Role of balanced fertilizers in increasing farmers' rice yields and profits

M. Zahidul Hoque and Md. Akhter Hossain Khan, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca., Bangladesh

To examine the potential of using recommended levels of balanced fertilizers, an experiment was conducted in a farmer's field at the BRRI cropping systems research site at Laskarchala in 1979 aus. The variety Chandina (BR1)

was used; the crop was transplanted, with supplemental irrigation. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Treatments consisted of 4 levels of fertilizer application: the farmer's level (26-47-0 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha), the recommended level for N + the farmers' level of P₂O₅ (80-47-0 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha), the recommended level for N-P₂O₅-K₂O (80-60-40 kg/ha), and the recommended level for N-P₂O₅-K₂O plus sulfur as SO₄ (80-60-40-34 kg/ha).

The yield was highest from the recommended level for NPK plus sulfur (4.3 t/ha), but it did not differ significantly from the treatment without sulfur (3.9 t/ha) (see table).

Replacing the farmer's level of N only with the recommended level significantly increased grain yield (3.3 t/ha vs 2.6 t/ha). Economic analysis of the extra costs and returns over the farmer's level indicated that investing an extra US\$16.57–31.53/ha could bring an extra net return of US\$129.00–372.28/ha. ■

Agroeconomic evaluation of extra nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and sulfur over the farmer's level of management in the 1979 aus at the Laskarchala BRRI Cropping Systems Research Site.

Treatment	Fertilizer rate (kg/ha)				Yield ^a (t/ha)	Added yield over farmer's level (t/ha)	Value of added yield (US\$/ha)	Cost of added inputs (US\$/ha)	Added profit over farmer's level (US\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	SO ₄						
1 ^b	26	47	0	0	2.6 c	–	–	–	–	–
2	80	47	0	0	3.3 b	0.6	145.58	16.57	129.01	7.7
3 ^c	80	60	40	0	3.9 a	1.3	308.51	26.63	281.88	10.5
4	80	60	40	34	4.3 a	1.7	403.80	31.53	372.28	11.8

^aCV = 6%. Mean yields with a common letter did not differ significantly at the 1% level. ^bFarmer's level. ^cRecommended level.

Varietal reaction of rice to age of seedlings transplanted in alkali soil

S. S. Singh, staff member, and Singh R. Deosharan, graduate student, Agronomy Department, Allahabad Agricultural Institute, Allahabad, U.P., India

An experiment conducted on an alkali soil (pH 8.2, ESP: 15.47%, and EC: 0.48 mmho/cm at 25°C) in 1977–78 kharif studied the effects of transplanting

seedlings of different ages. The split-plot design had varieties in the main plot and seedling age in the subplot. Fertilizer was applied at 120 kg N/ha (60 kg basal, 30 kg 20 days after transplanting [DT], and 30 kg at 40 DT irrespective of growth stage), 60 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 80 kg K₂O/ha as basal. Three healthy seedlings were transplanted in each hill.

The table shows that the period

required for establishment was not greatly influenced by the age of seedlings at transplanting. However, seedlings older than 25 days were established 1 or 2 days earlier. The time from panicle emergence to maturity generally was shorter in the short-duration variety Bala than in the medium-duration Ratna and the long-duration Sona. But in all three varieties, the time was shorter in seedlings